

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: NAYAK RAO****FIRST NAME: SHOBHAN****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401 D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. GULMA****List your 7 key concepts with the page number in text :**

1. Introduction (EUCLID2021, 7-10)
2. Process of academic essay Writing (EUCLID 2021, 7-10)
3. Formatting of academic essays (EUCLID 2021, 10-12)
4. Punctuations and language variants (EUCLID 2021, 15-22; 24-32)
5. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-39)

ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

I have done a preview of the ACA-401D as part of the introductory course for my program. The purpose of writing an academic essay is to communicate ideas based on evidence and seek answers to research hypotheses. The course provides a comprehensive preparatory course to communicate in the English language and prepares the student for the journey ahead. I think this approach will ensure research and post-doctoral students like me familiarize themselves and also unlearn and re-learn the fundamentals of language communications, style guides, and general academic writing. The contents of the ACA-401 course pack for period one provided me with a proper view of what lies ahead. It was also a refresher course for the English language for me. In this response paper, I discuss the process and structure of academic writing, the choice of an English language variant, and of rules of punctuation that affect academic essay writing. Further, I discuss the importance of style guides and how it is important to avoid plagiarism in academic essay writing.

2) PROCESS OF ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

An academic essay or scholarly writing is nonfictional writing produced as part of academic work (EUCLID 2021, 7). Examples of academic writing include research findings published in journals, books, newspapers, or other periodicals (or remain as manuscripts, theses, or dissertations), etc. The process of writing an academic or scholarly essay includes a definition of the problem, resource gathering, critical thinking/reading, essay planning, and writing coherently (EUCLID 2021, 7-14). I understand from the text that it is advisable to start early, define the problem in detail and analyze the writing task at hand. After understanding and defining what the writing task is about, the next step is to

gather all adequate resources on the topic. Sources of facts for academic essays must be from credible academic resources (EUCLID 2021, 9). After critical reading, thinking, and extracting meaningful information from credible sources the students need to organize his/her ideas and formulate them well. Thereafter the information gathered needs to be organized into a writing plan and structure. The writing plan involves ordering information in a logical scientific argumentative order (EUCLID 2021, 10) along with the constant revision of drafts all effectively contribute to the optimum writing of essays.

3) FORMATTING OF ACADEMIC ESSAYS

Academic essays follow a structure and organization that includes an introduction, body, and conclusion. In the introduction section of academic essays, the writer is encouraged to include information like a short topic orientation. (EUCLID 2021, 10). The body of the academic essay contains the details of the main ideas, including the pieces of evidence, analysis of the evidence, and leading statements to the next section of the body (EUCLID 2021, 10). The proper arrangement of these ideas into sections of main idea (M), pieces of evidence (E), analysis (A), and leading sentences (L). Writers should present academically established facts in a clear, concise manner, avoid repetitions and follow the laws of English Grammar as to punctuations, etc. Further, the analysis section should synthesize the writer's understanding of the pieces of evidence. In the conclusion section, the author restates their position about the question or writing task while also summarizing the main points from the body section (EUCLID 2021, 10).

4) LANGUAGE VARIANTS AND RULES OF USAGE

Academic essay writing is guided by certain rules to ensure the writers' right communication of ideas. Punctuations and language variants are two important rules that guide effective and consistent academic essay writing. Punctuations convey meanings to sentences (EUCLID 2021, 16). Apostrophes are also used to express contractions of two words in the English language. For e. g single quotation marks are used for indirect quotes and double quotation marks are used for direct speech. Depending on their position in a sentence, the colon and semi-colon determine the meanings of parts of the sentence. While the semi-colon links two related parts of a sentence, the colon connects unrelated parts. (EUCLID 2021, 19-23).

EUCLID (2021, 25) focuses on a chosen language variant of the English language that provides consistency and meaning in academic papers. The prominent variants are the British and American variants (EUCLID 2021, 25). These variants may have different spellings of some words, but convey the same meaning. Further, some words may be the same spelling but may convey additional meanings when used in some contexts. Other differences include the usage of punctuation, brackets, collective nouns, and plural adjectives.

5) PLAGIARISM

An essential part of the academic paper is originality. Plagiarism is when a writer fails to acknowledge the source of information in an academic paper (EUCLID 2021, 34). In other words, failure of an originality test can be regarded as plagiarism. The author needs to be able to convey his ideas in an original manner and language, giving full credit to the source of the information. In an academic paper, plagiarism can be expressed as direct quotes from a source, improper paraphrasing, or a direct copy of ideas without sufficiently referencing the source of information (EUCLID 2021, 34). Citations are established academic methods of avoiding plagiarism. Citations are implemented through in-text referencing.

6) CONCLUSION

The process and journey of an academic paper are governed by certain processes, rules, and frameworks. It is imperative that student must understand the structure and process of developing an academic essay, be familiar with the rules and constraints of avoiding plagiarism, implement and follow a style guide when developing and writing academic papers, and consider punctuations and variants of the English language in presenting ideas.

REFERENCES

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